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**The urbarium of Vohburg,
a market town in the Electorate of Bavaria, in the year 1672**

Philipp J. Heckmeier

The Bavarian city of Vohburg an der Donau has a rich history. However, little is known about the period after the Thirty Years' War (1648-1700), a blind spot in the city's history. There are some primary sources in the city's archive which have, until now, not been made accessible, including those regarding the years following the Swedish occupation, "Schwedenzeit", and the devastating war. One of the most important sources is the "Grund- und Salbuch", a register of land ownership, or "urbarium" of the town from 1672. This urbarium defines the town's possessions and names the inhabitants of Vohburg, together with details on their professions and their surroundings. The present work displays the urbarium in a fully transcribed form. The information from the urbarium is put in a geographical, sociological, and financial context and is used to reconstruct the townscape. The gained insights help to understand the forms of coexistence inside the town population at that time. This makes the "Grund- und Salbuch" extraordinarily valuable for Vohburg's local history and genealogy.

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Abstract

The Bavarian city of Vohburg an der Donau has a rich history. However, little is known about the period after the Thirty Years' War (1648-1700), a blind spot in the city's history. There are some primary sources in the city's archive which have, until now, not been made accessible, including those regarding the years following the Swedish occupation, "Schwedenzeit", and the devastating war. One of the most important sources is the "Grund- und Salbuch", a register of land ownership, or "urbarium" of the town from 1672. This urbarium defines the town's possessions and names the inhabitants of Vohburg, together with details on their professions and their surroundings. The present work displays the urbarium in a fully transcribed form. The information from the urbarium is put in a geographical, sociological, and financial context and is used to reconstruct the townscape. The gained insights help to understand the forms of coexistence inside the town population at that time. This makes the "Grund- und Salbuch" extraordinarily valuable for Vohburg's local history and genealogy.

Introduction

The city of Vohburg an der Donau has a multi-faceted history¹. Located around 15 km downstream from the Bavarian city Ingolstadt (Upper Bavaria), the present-day "Burgberg" (castle hill) of Vohburg, a rock outcrop above the Danube, was first settled in the Bronze Age – long before Germanic tribes migrated into present-day Bavaria. This was confirmed by archaeological excavations in 1973/1974². In the Middle Ages, a fortified castle was built on the "Burgberg", which was at that time located on a promontory between the meandering Danube, a branch of the Danube, and an estuary arm of the river Ilm³ (**Fig. 1**). To this day, this castle plays an important role in the historical analysis of Vohburg, mostly in terms of its medieval rulers⁴. The rulers of Vohburg were initially the Diepolding family⁵, before the castle passed into the possession of the Wittelsbach family in 1204. The legend of Agnes Bernauer, commonly known in contemporary Bavaria, dates from this period. According to the legend, Agnes Bernauer, the daughter of a barber from Augsburg, married the young Bavarian duke Albrecht III (1401-1460) at the castle of Vohburg. The marriage was not befitting the status and the barber's daughter was sentenced to be drowned in the Danube at Straubing (Lower Bavaria). Over the past centuries, the story has been historically illuminated⁶ and literarily interpreted⁷. It remains inextricably linked to Vohburg's castle on the castle hill.

Less is known about the market town at the foot of the castle hill. The scientific elucidation of the town itself starts with the early modern era, with Elisabeth Able's dissertation for the period 1745-1799⁸. Further back in time, only fragments and – in the best case – cornerstones are known, in particular for the 17th century and the Thirty Years' War. The latter hit the town disastrously and was accompanied with the ultimate destruction of the castle, a turning point for the town. In "Vohburg – Beiträge zur Geschichte der Stadt Vohburg und seiner Ortsteile", the local historian Max Kopp gives a brief overview of these key events in the religious wars of the 17th century⁹. According

¹ Kirschner, Max: Zur Geschichte der Stadt Vohburg. Vohburg 1978.

² Kirschner, Erwin: Bronzezeit-Funde auf dem Burgberg zu Vohburg. Sammelblatt des Historischen Vereins Ingolstadt, Volume 85. Ingolstadt 1976. pp. 139-148.

³ Kirschner, Erwin: Mittelalterliche Funde auf dem Burgberg zu Vohburg. Sammelblatt des Historischen Vereins Ingolstadt, Volume 86. Ingolstadt 1977. pp. 21-31.

⁴ Küss, Tobias: Die älteren Diepoldingen als Markgrafen in Bayern (1077-1204) – Adlige Herrschaftsbildung im Hochmittelalter. Herbert Utz Verlag, Munich 2013.

⁵ Flohrschütz, Günther: Studien zur Geschichte der Herrschaft Vohburg im Hochmittelalter. Sammelblatt des Historischen Vereins Ingolstadt, Volume 96. Ingolstadt 1987. pp. 9-83. Flohrschütz, Günther: Studien zur Geschichte der Herrschaft Vohburg im Hochmittelalter. Sammelblatt des Historischen Vereins Ingolstadt, Volume 97. Ingolstadt 1988. pp. 9-81.

⁶ Horchler, Gottfried: Agnes Bernauer in Geschichte und Dichtung. Attenkofer, Straubing 1883–1884. Riezler, Sigmund: Agnes Bernauerin und die bairischen Herzöge. Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Bayerischen Akademie der Wissenschaften. Munich 1885.

⁷ Hebbel, Friedrich: Agnes Bernauer. Munich 1851.

⁸ Able, Elisabeth: Ein kurbayerischer Markt in der Epoche des Reformabsolutismus. Vohburg an der Donau 1745-1799. Herbert Utz Verlag, Munich 2008.

⁹ Kopp, Max: Vohburg – Beiträge zur Geschichte der Stadt Vohburg und seiner Ortsteile. Vohburg 2017.

to that, it was the soldiers of the allied alliance troops who looted Vohburg in the early years of the war, between 1619 and 1632. At the same time, the town suffered from the plague and the dysentery. Then, the Swedes under King Gustavus Adolphus invaded Bavaria in the period 1630-1635, often referred to as the "Swedish War". In 1631, Swedish troops pillaged the market town, followed by the occupation under General Horn. In a push under General Baner, Swedish troops destroyed the castle and the schoolhouse in 1641 before occupying the town again between 1646 and 1648. After the Peace of Westphalia, only a third of the original population lived in the market town of Vohburg, then part of the Electorate of Bavaria.

Figure 1. City view of Vohburg an der Donau at the time of the Thirty Years' War. The copper engraving by Matthäus Merian¹⁰ shows the city from the south. Prominently, one can see the castle complex on a steep Jura hill, as well as the market square with the St. Andreas church and the “Kleines Donautor”, the Small Danube Gate – well-known as the landmark of the city. In front of this gate, there is an estuary of the river Ilm, called “Kleine Donau”, Small Danube.

From 1648 to 1700, after the horror of war, efforts were made to bring back normality to Vohburg. In the Vohburg City Archive (VCA), some documents fall into this period. These include the description of all fields in the "Lengenprunnerfeldt"¹¹ from 1664 (VCA B3) and the “Grund- und Salbuch”, an urbarium from 1672 (VCA B6; **Fig. 2**). The two documents, in particular the urbarium, documented and clarified the possessions in and around the town, which was probably not clearly defined after the years of war turmoil. The urbarium was a common form of documentation at the time. It was used by landlords to record their property, the rights and income associated with it¹². Today, urbaria are of particular interest in an economic and historical context¹³. In addition to VCA B3 and B6, there are also documents from the years 1659, 1678 and 1694 (VCA U5-7), council minutes from the years 1671-1673 (VCA B 1-2 and B 1-3), as well as a blacksmith book from 1699 (VCA B7). For the year 1672, both the urbarium and the council minutes are available as primary sources. However, both sources are neither transcribed nor historically analyzed.

In Vohburg's history, the post-war period from 1648 to 1700 is still poorly understood. The detailed analysis of the electoral market of Vohburg by Elisabeth Able only covers the period 1745-1799¹⁴. In order to get the most

¹⁰ Merian, Matthäus: *Topographia Bavariae*. Frankfurt 1644.

¹¹ This field was in the north of Vohburg, i.e. on the other side of the Danube near Menning, adjoining the chapel of ‘Seliger Bauer’. This can be deduced from the posthumous notes of the local historian Joseph Pflügl, as well as from the unpublished transcription of VCA B3 by Max Kopp and Erwin Kirscher.

¹² Hägermann, Dieter: „Urbar“, *Lexikon des Mittelalters*, Band VIII. Stuttgart/Weimar 1999, 1286–1289. Dubler, Anne-Marie. „Urbare“, *Historisches Lexikon der Schweiz (HLS)*, Version from 14.01.2014. Online: <https://hls-dhs-dss.ch/de/articles/008953/2014-01-14/>, accessed on April 10, 2022.

¹³ Schrenk, Christhard: *Methoden der Auswertung frühneuzeitlicher Urbare am Beispiel des Orsinger Urbars von 1758*. Schriften des Vereins für Geschichte des Bodensees und seiner Umgebung, Volume 102. Friedrichshafen, 1984, pp. 153–162.

¹⁴ Able, Elisabeth. 2008.

comprehensive insight into what was happening in the city after the Thirty Years' War, a detailed analysis of the existing primary sources from the VCA is necessary. The "Grund- und Salbuch", the urbarium from this period, plays a central role to list agricultural areas, buildings in the town, and details on who lived and worked there in 1672. A large number of people are given with full names, along with their professions, their neighbors or their role in Vohburg. This underlines the importance of the urbarium not only from a historical but also from a genealogical point of view.

This article provides the German transcription of the urbarium and comments it in the historical and genealogical context of the city. Aim of this study is to gain a better understanding of the possessions of the town, but even more, of its social structures. In this article, names are given to the persons who formed the urban life in 1672 and rebuilt Vohburg after the devastating war. An economic analysis of the financial situation of the electoral market is expressly not in the focus, however, all listed positions are briefly outlined in a short chapter. In summary, this study is the first attempt to draw an overall picture of Vohburg's recovery after the Thirty Years' War.

Methods

The digitized version of VCA B6 was made available to the author by the VCA. It is written entirely in German Gothic handwriting, "Kurrent". The transcription of the urbarium is word and letter accurate. The lack of distinction between the capital letters "U" and "V" and the capitalization of all "Z" and "V" at the beginning of a word were adopted from the original. The use of "f" and "ß" as well as "ff" is unsteady in some cases, which makes it difficult to transcribe the letter (e.g., fol. 3r, third section: "Hieronimuss" and "Schißhaus"). In order to keep the transcription as objective as possible, these characters were consistently translated with the Latin "s" (see "Hieronimus" and "Schishaus"). Terms that are meant less known from today's perspective are explained in footnotes, supported by the help of Reinhard Riepl's "Wörterbuch zur Familien- und Heimatforschung in Bayern und Österreich"¹⁵.

The places mentioned in the urbarium were reconstructed in Fig. 5. The basis for the reconstruction was an old map of Vohburg an der Donau from 1813, which can be viewed on the "Bayerische Landesbibliothek Online", as well as the "BayernAtlas" of the "Bayerisches Staatsministerium für Finanzen und für Heimat". When creating this reconstruction, the outlines of the town center were roughly transferred, aware of a possible discrepancy with the earlier conditions. The map is therefore only an aid to present the loose location information from the "Grund- und Salbuch" as comprehensibly as possible.

¹⁵ Riepl, Reinhard: Wörterbuch zur Familien- und Heimatforschung in Bayern und Österreich. 3rd Edition. Waldkraiburg 2009.

Figure 2. Title page of “Grund- und Salbuches des kurfürstlichen Marktes Vohburg“ from 1672.

Transcription

Title

Gründt: und Sall
Büech

Chürfr: Marckhts Vohbürg

Aufgericht Anno

1672

fol. 1r

Erstlichen befindetet sich in dem Marckht Vohburg auf dem Plaz, unweith Von der St. Andrae Khürchen alda, das dem Gmain Marckth der ohrten, eigenthomblich angehörige Rhathaus, mit den undten herumb underschidlichen Handwerchsläden, und darin Verhandtnen Brodthaus, Von welchen Jerlichen ab den Inhabern, auf Versuechen, und widerrueffen Stüfftgelt geraicht: und Gmainen Markht in der Camerrechnung per Einnamb gebracht würdt.

(Rand: mit anderer Hand) Rathaus

Von Ludwigen Prompper, Burger und Brodthiettern¹⁶ alhie, so im Rhathaus ain Stibl und Cammer Stüfftweis bewohnt. / 3 fl

Dermallen befindenet sich fünf Pökhen¹⁷ Zu Vohburg, deren Nannen Johann Winhardt, Tobias Winhardt, Mathias Winhardt, Hanns Schwarzgrebmer, und Geörg Schreder, und ieder aus einem Standt Jerlich 30 kr Stüfftgelt gibt, macht / 2 fl, 30 kr

fol. 1v

Von den 3 Fleischpankhen, welche Adam Prunner, Sebastian Schefthaller, und Hanns Koch, die drey alhieigen Mezger Stüfftweis inhaben, gibt ieder Jerlich 2 fl 30 kr macht. / 7 fl, 30 kr

Simon Khueffer, eussern Rhats Crammer alhie, bezalt aus seinem im Rhathaus herundt habenten Stüfftladen. / 3 fl

Michael Prändl Sailer der ohrten, ab seinem Stüfftladen am Rhathaus alle Jar. / 1 fl

Thoma Trattner Hafner alhie, von ain dergleichen Laden. / 1 fl, 20 kr

Ebenfals Jacob Rapp Hafner alhie, ab solchem Stüfftladen. / 1 fl, 20 kr

fol. 2r

Geörg Wagner, Burger und Melbler der ohrten auch Von ainem Laden im Rhathaus. Jerlich / 1 fl, 20 kr

Aus der Viertten Fleischpankh so dermall mit khain Mezger besezt, raicht Ludwig Prompper Brodthietter, welcher sein Holz darein legt, Stüfftgelt. / 40 kr

Die Wohnung auf dem clain Thonnauthor¹⁸, warbei ain redo.¹⁹ Ställel auf 3 Stuckh Vich, und negst ausserhalb des Thors ain claines Gärttl, so alles Zu Gmain Markht gehörig, bewohnt der alhie aufgestelte Burgerdiener Simon Seidl, wie sein antecessor²⁰, ohne Zins,

(Rand: mit anderer Hand) Kleines Donautor

¹⁶ Bread supervisor

¹⁷ Baker

¹⁸ Small Danube Gate

¹⁹ Riepl, Reinhard. Short version for *reverendo* = filthy, stinking; in this case as an excuse for the usage of the following words.

²⁰ Predecessor

Item²¹ das Thor bey der Grossen Thonnau, welches Wolf Weng, ietzt dessen Sohn Andre Wenng sambt der undten Verhandten Schlosserschmit, als ain Schlosser, gegen raichung des Stüfftgels im Inhaben und Jerlich dafür Zalt / 5 fl

(Rand: mit anderer Hand) Grosses Donautor

fol. 2v

Die ober Stuben erstgemelten²² Thors besüzt Marthin Renner, alhieiger Burger und Tagwercher, und Zalt Jerlich Stüfftgelt. / 2 fl, 30 kr

Geörg Paucher Freymezger alhie, gibt aus der bei obigen Thor Verhandtnen Fleischfreypanckh, Stüfftgelt, oder Zins. / 1 fl, 30. kr

Bey ersagter Freypankh, hat Gmainer Markht, ain clain blosses Heusl, darin ain Stibl und Cämerl, aus welchem dermalliger Inhaber Balthasar Grabmair Maurer Zins gibt / 4 fl

In dennen Wohnungen bei dem dritt Gemainem Markht Zugehörigem Author, allwo auch Zwo Stüben, und Zwo Cämer, sein dermall ganz alt erarmbte Burgersleith, Als Georg Pauman, und sein Weib, das alt: und Junge Seellweib²³, Umbsonst in der Herberg.

(Rand: mit anderer Hand) Autor

fol. 3r

Von dem Gemainen Markh gehörigem Schuelhaus aufm Perg, Zwischen Wolf Hueber Glasern, und Sebastian Khueffer Schneidern, gibt besizenter Maller Constantinus Dosch Jerliches Stüfftgelt. / 2 fl

(Rand: mit anderer Hand) Schulhaus auf dem Berg

Der beyr Grossen Thonau Zum Markh gehörige Pruckhstadel ist weiter niemandt Verstüfftet, sondern würdtet das bedürfftige Pruckhholz, und anders was man bey der Pruckh bedürfftig, aufbehalten.

(Rand: mit anderer Hand) Brückenstadel

Simon Liebhardt Tagwercher, gibt aus der Herberg im gmain Markht gehörigen Schishaus auf der Pälzen²⁴, negst Hieronimus Miller Wagners Haus Zu Jerlichen Stüfftgelt. / 4 fl

(Rand: mit anderer Hand) Schießhaus auf der Beizen, später Rieper

Aus dem Hietthaus, bey dem Spitalgraben alhie, negst den Gabersthailen, raicht der darauf verhandtne redo. Wasenmaister²⁵ Geörg Litter Zu alhieigen Markht Stüfft / 2 fl

(Rand: mit anderer Hand) Hüthaus beim Spitalgraben, später Wasenmeister

fol. 3v

Caspar Lehner alhieiger Weisgerber, gibt aus seiner Weisgerber Werchstatt bey der clain Thonnau, negst Marthin Hörmann Vischers, Zu Jerlichen Stüfftgelt. / 45 kr

(Rand: mit anderer Hand) HsN²⁶ 2

Bärtholome Schneider Schmit am Gries alhie, wegen seiner auf Gmain Markhts Grundt erpauthen Schmidtstatt, Jerlichen Zins. / 30 kr

(Rand: mit anderer Hand) HsN 188

Ludwig Khienner Gerichtspoth, und Burger alhie, ab ainem bey seiner Behausung am Gries, erpauthen redo. Schwein Stallel, Jerlich Gült Zu Gmain Markht. / 6 kr

²¹ Latin expression for „likewise“.

²² former

²³ “Seelfrauen” worked in “Seelhaus”/almshouse and took care of the poor, the sick, and the dying. Their task was i.a. to wash the corpses.

²⁴ Today’s name: “Baizen”.

²⁵ Knacker

²⁶ House number

Dann Melchior Pauman Leinweber alhie, aus ainem Gärttl negst den Augärten bstendtige Gült. / 7 kr

(Rand: mit anderer Hand) ... 1693 ...

Thoman Pökh²⁷ Burger, und dermall Khiehietter²⁸, aus ainem bey seinem Haus ausser des Authors, eingefangnem Gärttl eingelgte Gült. / 3 kr

fol. 4r

Bey dem Markht Vohburg sein 34 erpauthe Gmainheuser aus welchem ieder Inhaber Jerlichen Zur Cammer Cassa²⁹ 10 kr Gült bezallen mus. Und sint die iezigten Besitzer

Hans Wolf, Burger und Tagwercher alhie, aus seiner inhabenten Gmainbehausung, hinter der Pürg, neben Hannsen Khormillern, und Andre Hofner Maurers Heusern, Jerlich / 10 kr

Hanns Khormiller auch Tagwercher auch von seiner Gmainbehausung hinter der Pürg, neben obgedachten Hanns Wolfen, und Geörgen Grädls Heusern. / 10 kr

Phillipp Rorekher Burger, und Zimerman Zu Vohburg, ab seinem ans Author stossenden Gmainhaus. / 10 kr

Nicolaus Matthes Vischer, Von sein Gmainhaus, negst des Oxengraben³⁰, und Wolf Mez Vischers. / 10 kr

fol. 4v

Willibaldt Schneider Wagner, hat auch ain Gmainhaus Zwischen Jacob Zollinger, und Wolf Mez Vischern. / 10 kr

Jacob Zollinger Vischer, von sein Gmainhaus, negst der Grosse-THONAU, und obgedachten Wagners. / 10 kr

Wolf Mez auch ein Gmainhaus, neben Willibaldt Schneider Wagners, und Nicla Mathes Vischers. / 10 kr

Veith Mathes Inneren Rhats Vischer, aus seiner Gmainbehausung negst undten an der Grosse Thonau, und Gmain Markhts Pruckhstahl. / 10 kr

Marthin Hörman eusserm Rhats Vischer, ain Gmainhaus bei der clain Thonaupruckhen und des clain Thonauthors. / 10 kr

Michael Widtman Burger und Tagwecher, aus seinem Gmainhaus neben Jacob Eyring auch Tagwercher, und Wolf Pless Vischern / 10 kr

fol. 5r

Sebalt Maister, Lederer im Gmainhaus negst Marthin Hörman, und Geörgen Rorekher Zimermaistern. / 10 kr

Leonhardt Wüntter Vischer ain Gmainhaus, neben obigen Rorekher, und Peter Engseugl Vischern. / 10 kr

Erstgemalter Peter Engseugel, ab seinem Gmainhaus Zwischen oberierten Leonhardt Wüntter Vischern, und Thoma Huebern Tagwerchern. / 10 kr

Ludwig Khienner Burger, und Gerichtspoth alhie, aus dessen Gmainhaus, neben obigen Thoma Hueber und Caspar Weltmair Tagwerchern. / 10 kr

Geörg Rorekher Zimermaister, ab seinem Gmainbehausung, Zwischen Marthin Hörman Vischers, und Sebalt Maister Lederers. / 10 kr

fol. 5v

Jacob Eyring Burger, und Tagwercher alhie, hat ain Gmainhaus, zwischen Michael Widtman Tagwerchern, und Geörg Seiz auch Tagwerchern. / 10 kr

²⁷ Pölkh (see later mentions)

²⁸ Cowherd

²⁹ Financial management of the municipality.

³⁰ Located between "Auertor", today's Hohenstaufenstraße, and the Danube; will be further defined in the Analysis section.

Hanns Liebhardt Tagwercher, aus seinem Gmainhaus, neben Hieronimus Miller Wagnern, und Niclasen Rieschl Webers auf der Pälzen. / 10 kr

(Rand: mit anderer Hand – kaum leserlich) ... 1679

Jacob Schmit Schneider ab dessen Gmainhaus, Zwischen Zacharias Eyring Webern, und Anna Schneiderin Wittiben, auch auf der Pälzen. / 10 kr

Michael Eyring Vischer Von dessen Gmainhaus am Graben, negst Sebastian Scheftthaller Mezgern, und Hanns Khienast Leinwebern. / 10 kr

Hanns Furthmer, iezt Thoman Hueber Tagwercher, aus dem Gmainhaus neben Peter Engseugl Vischern, und Ludwig Khiener Ghrtspoth³¹. / 10 kr

fol. 6r

Anna Seizin Wittib, Von ainem Gmainhaus auf der Pälzen alhie, neben Jacob Schmit Schneidern, und Geörgen Hiemair aldorthen. / 10 kr

Hieronimus Miller Wagner, ab dessen Gmainhaus auf der Pälzen, neben Hannsen Liebhardt, und Mathes Daser, beeden Tagwerchern. / 10 kr

Geörg Grädl Tagwercher, ab desselben Gmainhaus hinter der Pürg, neben Hanns Kormiller, und dem Au graben. / 10 kr

Andre Reitter Schuechmacher, aus seiner Behausung am Griss, Zwischen Jacoben Eyring, und Geörgen Seiz, beeden³² Tagwerchern. / 10 kr

Jacob Veichtmair Pfeiffer Von seiner Behausung, Vorm Author, neben Thoma Pölkhen, und Leonhardt Raucheggern, beeden Alhieig Tagwerchern. / 10 kr

fol. 6v

Thoman Pölkh Tagwercher, aus dessen Gmainbehausung Vorm Author, neben Jacob Veichtmair Pfeiffern, und dem Oxengraben. / 10 kr

Hanns Schelshorn Vischer, ab sein Gmainhaus neben dem Author, an den Oxengraben stossent. / 10 kr

Michael Zieribl Tagwercher, Von sein Haus am Griess, Zwischen Bärtlme Schneidern Schmit, und Caspar Lehner Weisgerbers Werchstatt. / 10 kr

Bartholome Schneider Schmit, aus seinen Gmainhaus neben obigen Zoribl³³, dan Wolf Pless Vischern. / 10 kr

Caspar Weltmair Tagwercher, ab sein Gmainhaus am Griess, neben des Gerichtspoth, Ludwigen Khienner, und Gemain Markhts Hietthaus, so der redo. Wasnmaister bewohnt. / 10 kr

fol. 7r

Andre Hofner, Burger, und Maurer alhie, von sein Gmainhaus auf der Pürg, neben dem Augarben³⁴, und Hanns Wolf Tagwerchern. / 10 kr

Wolf Pless Vischer, gibt aus sein Gmainhaus am Griess neben Bärtlme Schneidern Schmit, und Michael Wüdtman Tagwerchern, wie all andre. / 10 kr

Adam Rhormair Tagwercher, Von dessen am Au graben, Zwischen des Reicharten Steichel, und besagten Au grabens ligenten Gmainhaus / 10 kr

Leonhardt Rauchegger Tagwercher, ab dessen Vorm Author, neben Jacoben Veichtmair Pfeiffers³⁵ ligenten Gmainhaus auch / 10 kr

³¹ Court messenger

³² both

³³ Putatively Michael Zieribl.

³⁴ "Augraben"

³⁵ Musician

fol. 7v

Paull Strassers gewesten Bürgers alhie seel:³⁶ Hofstatt, so seith des 1632 eingefallen Schwedischen Kriegs, noch ödt, und neben Wolf Hafner iezigen Färbers alhie Gartten, dan Michael Thalhammer Schneiders der ohrten Haus ligt, ist Vor disem auch ain Gmainhaus gwest, und mues nach erpauung derselben, ebenfals Von dem Inwohner geraicht werden. / 10 kr

Gleiche Mainung³⁷ hat es mit Hanns Eisenmairs seel: Von obiger Zeit an ödt Verhandtnen Hofstatt, negst des Simon Burgers, Burgers, und churfürstl: Casstenkhechts, dan Wolf Hueber Glasers beeden alhie, Heusern, aus welcher auch ein Inhaber, weils Vor disem auch ain Gmainhaus gwest, Jerlichen geben muss. / 10 kr

fol. 8r

Zwischen der Gross, und clainen Thonau, underhalb des Markhts, ist ain an etlichen ohrten mit Aichreis, und andrem Wildten Obstpaumen angewaxner Gries, welcher Völlig Zu Gmain Markh gehörig, auch die darin Verhantne Vichwaidt zu der Burgerschaft nuzen, der alhie aufgestellte redo. Wasenmaister Geörg Litter aber, hat in ersagtem Gries bei ainem Tagwerch Wismath³⁸ gros ausgereitt, und hinaus ain Wismath gemacht, ab disem mus Er Jerlichen, so lang es ihme gelassen wüdt Zu Gemainem Markht angelegtes Stüfftgelt raichen / 1 fl, 8 kr, 4 hl

Sebastian Tanner Loderer Zu Vohburg, hat man in ernanten Gries bei der clain Thonau, ainen Lodnerramb aufzurichten Verwilligt, Von welcher Er aber Jerlichen Zins geben muss. / 8 kr, 4 hl

fol. 8v

In Vorerantem Gries, ist ain auch dem Gmain Markht zuegehöriger Gabesgärtt, eingezeunter, mit 128 Pifang, oder Gabesthaill, dise haben die Burger Zu ihren Burgersheusern, ieder ain thaill zeniessen, dagegen aber mues ieglicher den Zaun, so weith sein pflanz: oder Gabesthaill geth, erhalten, und Jerlichen Zu Gmain Markht, ab ieden thaill bezalt werden. / 4 kr

#³⁹

Gleichermassen sein in dem Pruckhveldt bey der Burgerlichen Neumill 130 dergleichen, Gabesthaill, alwo abermaller ieder Burger ainen thaill zu Zuniessen, gegen erhaltung des Zauns, und raichung. / 4 kr

Negstdeme befindet sich ain clains Gabesgärttl die Neuprich in dem Himelreich genant, haltet 12 Gabesthaill, und gibt ieder Inhaber, wie obige, ab ainen thaill auch, / 4 kr

fol. 9r

Underhalb der Pälzen, negst der clain Thonau, ist ain Zu Gmain Markht gehörigen Pflanzgarten, darein alhiege Burger, wer heuslichen ansessig, die Notturfft pflanzen, ohne bezallung oder abgab eines Zins, pauen khönnen, Ausser des Markhts beileiffig ainer Viertelstundt weith, hat Gemainer Markh ain Burgerliche Mill, so die Neumill genant, an der Ilm ligent, so Vermög eines alt Verhandtnen gdisten⁴⁰ Confirmationsbriefs Von Hörzog Stephan in Bayrn hochselligster gedechtnus, anno 1398 zerpauen gnedigis Verwilligt worden. mit ainer dabey Verhandtnem Saagmill, dise bewohnt dermallen Andre Heuss Neumiller, welcher zwar Zu Gemainem Markh weither khain andere Gült noch dienst: sondern nur seine belegt burgerliche onera⁴¹ als Steuer servigelter⁴² und anders wie ain andrer Burger entrichten mues, doch weillen ihme Miller

fol. 9v

Von ersagtem Mackht, auf diser Mill, und hierzu gehörigen Grundstuckhen, Erbtgerechtigkeit Verlichen, mues dieser und andere Inhaben, auf Verenderung der Erbrecht, Zu Gemainen Markht: Vom 100: 5 fl Anstandt, und Abfarth⁴³ pro cento 2 fl 30 kr bezallen.

³⁶ Abbr. for "selig" = already passed away.

³⁷ Riepl, Reinhard. Order, regulation.

³⁸ Riepl, Reinhard. Area, used for haying / hay harvest.

³⁹ Insertion at the end.

⁴⁰ Riepl, Reinhard. Abbr. for "gnädigst" = gracious.

⁴¹ Riepl, Reinhard. Public charges, taxes.

⁴² Riepl, Reinhard. Rent compensation.

⁴³ Riepl, Reinhard. Charges when taking over/giving up a property.

Zu diser Mill gehörn zwen dem Markh eigenthombliche Äckher, deren der erste im Obern Auveltdt bei gedachter Neumill, Zwischen des churfürstl: Gerichtschreibers alhie, Herrn Georgen Vetter, und eines churfürstl: Fronlehenackhers ligt, halt 70 Pifang, und würdt der Stiglackher genant, der andere Ackher ligt Zwischen des Millweegs, und des Wassers, stosst auf ain alhieigen Gottsheusern gehörige paint⁴⁴, herunden auf die ringgassen, ist mit ainem Zaun umbfangen, und halt bei zwo Einsez⁴⁵.

In dem Underriedt, unweith von der besagten Mill, ist ain eingezeunter Garten, dabey ain halbs Tagwech

fol. 10r

Wismath, so vor alters die Zillwekhin genant, stosst an Hannsen Widtman von Menning, und Geörgen Dopplen Preuens⁴⁶ Zu Vohburg Wisen.

Und lesstens ain halbs Tagwerch Wismath. die Thürwis genant, so ieziger Inhaber Heuss, nach Verwilligen Ackhermessig gemacht, ligt Zwischen des churfürstl: Preuverwalters Zu Kelhaimb, Herrn Johann Spizweggs, der ohrtem habenten Wisen, und Bärtholomeen Neuhauser Millers zu Harakher, auch aines Zu alhieigen Gottsheusern gehörigen Ackher.

Volgen die Zum Marckht Vohburg eigenthomblich gehörige Wisen.

Erstlichen, ist negst des Markhts Author, ain einzeuntes Tagwerch Wismath, der Oxengraben genant, stosst hinaus auf die gross Thonau, herein an Hanns Schelsthorn Vischers Haus, diese wisen hat alhieiger Auhietter

fol. 10v

Phillipp Rorekher, weill Er, und andere Auhietter herkhomnermassen, bei der Vohburgischen Khieherdt, ainen Fahroxen ohne der Burger entgelt halten mus, umbsonst ohne raichung aines Zins, zenuzen⁴⁷.

In dem Undern Auveltdt, hat gedachter Rorekher von Gmain Markht Vier Tagwerch Wismath, welches mit ainem ohr, an ainen alhieigen Gottheusern gehörigen Ackher, und andern an einem chrfrstl: Casstenamtsackher⁴⁸, das Bärtholome Neuhauser Millers Zu Hartakher Ackher stosst, dermallen aber auch dem Auhietter Zu seinen dienst ohne Zins gelassen ist, Geörg Rorekher Pruckhmaistern alhie ist nitweniger ain Wissen im Undern Auveltdt mit drey Tagwerchen, so herund an ainem Zu alhieigen Beneficium⁴⁹ gehörigen Akher, andern ohr Gallien⁵⁰ Schiechel, Burger Zu Vohburg stosst, auch an Wolf Hafner Färber, dan Georgen Rhaittens beeden der ohrten Äckher gelegen, Zu seinem Pruckhmaisterdienst, Vom Gmain Markht umbsonst Verlassn

fol. 11r

In dem Underriedt Am Lehrpuckhl, Zwischen ainer Zu alhieigen Gottheusern gehörigen Wisen, und ainer Spitalwisen, am Lehrgraben stossent, hat Gemainer Markht Vier Tagwerch Zwimadiges Wismath, und dises Wismath, thuet alle Jar ain andres Markhts Viertl ordentlich lessen⁵¹, und mues ieder Inhaber der im Los heraus khombt, Vom Tagwerch Zur Cammer Cassa selbiges Jar bezallen. / 36 kr

Gleiche Bschaffenheit hat es mit dem Wismath, so man die zway Tagwerch nent, und ebenfals Zwimadig ist, so in dem Underriedt Zwischen ainer churfürstl: Cassten Wisen, dan Wolfen Aman Zu Dinzing, stosst herab an ain heyl:⁵² Wisen, Zu alhieigen Gottsheusern gehörig, und hinauf auf die Aff?erlohe, gegen ersagtem Amanpaurn, Umb dises Wismath thuen aus obigen Viertl, auch die Burger lessen, und werden 5 Taill daraus gemacht, ab welchen ieder Zum Markht gibt / 28 kr

fol. 11v

Wider ain Wismath in gedachtem Unterriedt, so ainmädig, und 6 Tagwerch haltent, stosst auf ain Wis der Eglsee genant, andern ohr ans Ilmerdorffer Veldt, gegen Bärtholome Prunauern, Burger Zu Vohburg. Dise 6

⁴⁴ Riepl, Reinhard. "Peunt" = fenced meadow (for special management); not subject to any agricultural constraints.

⁴⁵ Unit for half yoke.

⁴⁶ Brewer

⁴⁷ Putatively: "zu nutzen" = to use.

⁴⁸ Riepl, Reinhard. "Kastenamt" = management of the Sovereign's property.

⁴⁹ Church foundation

⁵⁰ Version of the name Gallus

⁵¹ to draw lots; some of the acres and meadows owned by the municipality were given to the citizens in an annual lottery.

⁵² "Heiling-Wiese": meadow which is owned by the church (church foundation = "Heiling").

Tagwerch werden auch Jerlichen den Vohburgischen Burgern im Los Verlassen; doch mues ieder Vom Tagwerch geben / 24 kr

Negst der Neumill bei alhieigem Markhts Gabesgarten, im Pruckhveldt genant, sein 3 Tagwerch Wismath. stossen an ain zu alhieigen St. Andrae Beneficium gehörige Wisen, andern ohrt, an Michael Hekhmair Innern Rhats Preuen Zu Vohburg seint Zwimädig, und würdt auch wie oben Jerlichen Burgern Verlassen, davon ieder ab seinen thail raichen mues. / 20 kr

Beim Dorf Zu Harakher, sein Vier Tagwerch Zwimädigs Wismath, die Furthwisn genant, neben Hanns Knöferl Paurns Zu Harthamb Wisen, stosst herein werths

fol. 12r

gegen der Harakher Gmain, hinaus auf Sebastian Hueber, Paur Zu Pleyling. Würdt Jerlichen im obigen formb 4 Burgern alhie Verlassen, und Von iedem eingenommen. / 18 kr

Dann ain Wismath die Sechzger genant, bestehen in 7 Tagwerch ainmädig, stosst an Vorbeschribne Dreyschilling Wisen, dan aufs Ilmerdorffer Veldt, und den Eglsee, solches Wismath haben Jerlich 7 Burger Zuniessen, und mues ieder davon geben ab ainem Tagwerch. / 16 kr

Mehr 12 Tagwerch ainmädiges Wismath, bey der Welln, an alhieige Gottsheuser Wismather stossent, neben dem Irschinger Mos, Von disen 12 Tagwerch, haben die alhieigen drey Khiehietter Namens Thoma Pölk, Jacob Schöberl, und Leonhardt Rauchegger, wegen der Khiehuet, wie Von disem ieder ain Tagwerch umbsonst,

fol. 12v

auch hievon der Auhietter Phillipp Rorekher drey Tagwerch wegen seines Diensts ohne Zins Zuniessen, Von den ybrigen 6 Tagwerchen, so Zu Zeiten wegen schlechten haugets gar nicht eingemäht werden, geben die ienigen so es Stüfften, Jerlich Zusammen. / 28 kr

In dem Underiedt ligt ain einzeunts Wisl, $\frac{3}{4}$ Tagwerch haltent, Zwischen einer churfrtl: Cassten-Ambts: und Jacob Haider Preuens seel: Wittib Barbara, Wisen, stosst mit ainem ohrt an alhiege Pfarwisn, welche dem Burgerdiener Simon Seidl ohne Zins Zu seinem Dienst gelassen würdt.

Vorgedachter Geörg Rhorekher Pruckhmaister, hat mehrmallen Vom Gmain Markht ain halb Tagwerch Zwimädiges Wisl im besagten Underiedt, neben ein churfrstl: Cassten: und Bärtlme Neuhauser Millers zu Harakher Wisen, so auf die Ilm stosst, Ohne Zins, so lang Er den dienst hat, Zeniessn.

fol. 13r

Ausserhalb Harackher, ist ain Wismat das Mos genant, gehet ain Graben dardurch, welches Wismath, so weither nit eingemäht würdt, mit dem Vohburgisch Landtgerichtischen Dorf Harackher also in der Gmain, das sowoll die Dorffsbegriffne, als alhieige Burger, nach Ihrem gfallen darin mähen, und grasen derffen. Wie sy dan auf bedürfftigen Fall, obigen Graben Zu gleich miteinander miessen raumen lassen, negst disem Mos, haben auch die Vohburgisch Und Harakherischen Khiehietter miteinander 6 Tagwerch Wismath welche auf das Grieshammermos stossen, ohne Zins Zuniessen.

Volgen die Äckher.

Bey disem Markh sein drey Äckher, hirunder ligt der erste ausser der Pälzen mit Vir Pifang, in den Krauttgärten, stosst oben, und unden auf ainen Zaun.

fol. 13v

Zwischen der Heuser, und Caspar Lehner alhieigen Weiserbers Khrauttgärttl,

Das ander im Mitterfeldt mit 20 Khurz und langen Pifangen, stosst oben auf ainen alhieigen Widenackher, unden auf den Weeg, Zwischen Hanns Wippinger Khueffers: und der Herrn Königischen Erben alhie äckher,

Dritter akher, so der Thaimbakher genant, ligt Zwischen aines Weegs: und Leonhardt Wüntter alhieigen Vischers stosst gegen dem Markht auf Reichardten Scheuderen Vischer, oben auf einen Fahrtweeg, halt khurz, und lang bey 40 Pifang, dise erstbemelte 3 Äkher hat der alhieige Rhatdienner Simon Seidl, wegen seines Diensts, ohne raichung aines Zins zuniessen.

fol. 14r

An Holzwachsen

Ist Zum Gmain Markht eigenthomblich das Auholz, unweith von dem Markht, neben dr Grosse Thonau, stosst oben bis an das Auerholz, an der Irschinger und anderen Wismath, desstwegen die Inhaber derselben die Zeun halten miessen, dises Holz gehet hinumb bis auf das alt: oder Grasig Wassr, alwo die Welln darein Rhint, auch gegen alhieigen Markh bis an die Ilm und clain Thonau.

Und lesstens im Undern Auveltd ain clains gestreissl, das gstokhet genant.

(Unterzeichnet:)

Simon Khueffer
Tobias Winhardt
Michael Hekhmair
Eggidius Fiedler
Sebastian Scheffthaller
Wolfgang Hafner

(Handschriftliche Anmerkung zu fol. 8v aus dem 18. Jahrhundert:)

den 13. Maij anno 1748

Seint uf vorher beschehen undertheniges erbitten nachstehenten Burgern in dem sogenannten Plaichgries 8 gabes thail, gegen erlag 5 fl vor ieden und Jehrl. raichung 4 x Zins, ausgezaigt worden, als

Johann Georg Kreythmayr Bürgl. Strimpfstricher und Brothitter1 Gabesthaill
Mathias Euringer Tagwercher1 Gabesthaill
Mathias Wüntter Vischer1 Gabesthaill
Mathias Elend Tagwercher1 Gabesthaill
Johann Dobolanzko Naglschmid1 Gabesthaill
Augustin Raith Schreiner1 Gabesthaill
Max Kölbel pott und Veith Fiedler Tagwercher miteinander1 Gabesthaill
Bartlmee Wüntter und Gregori Purghart Schuechmacher auch miteinander1 Gabesthaill

Analysis

The urbarium of the market town of Vohburg in 1672 can be divided into eight sections. These are:

1. The premises in the town hall (fol. 1r-2r; **Fig. 3**).
2. The living areas/premises in the three city gates, in the schoolhouse “Schulhaus”, in the shooting range “Schießhaus”, in the house the local knacker, “Hüthaus”, as well as other buildings and gardens that belonged to the municipality in the urban area (fol. 2r,2v).
3. All communal houses “Gmainhäuser” that belonged to the market town and were let to citizens, called “Burger”, and residents without citizenship (fol. 3r-7v).
4. The “Gries”⁵³ area east of the town (fol. 8r) and the community gardens, called “Gabesgärten” (fol. 8v).
5. The civil mill “Neumühle” south of the town with its fields and meadows (fol. 9r-10r).
6. All meadows belonging to the town (fol. 10r-13r).
7. The few fields that the town owned (fol. 13r,13v).
8. The forest stock of the town, which is not extensive, titled “Holzwachsen” (fol. 14r).

At the end, the urbarium was signed by Simon Khueffer, Tobias Winhardt, Michael Hekhmair, Eggidius Fiedler, Sebastian Scheffthaller and Wolfgang Hafner (**Fig. 4**). On the last page there are additional handwritten notes from 1748 on “Gabesgärten” in “Plaichgries”.

Figure 3. Description of the town hall.

⁵³ Land reclamation by sand, at a river

Geographical Interpretation

The sober, but nevertheless very detailed descriptions in the urbarium give impressive insights into Vohburg's urban life in the years after the Thirty Years' War. In many cases, the specifications in the urbarium allow a geographical classification of the residential or working areas of the named persons in Vohburg.

The town hall was in the center of the community. Unlike today's situation, it was not Vohburg's St. Andreas church, but was in close proximity to it, on today's market square. The former town hall building was later demolished (1811) and replaced by a building that served as a boys' school until 1971, before it was demolished again in 1981⁵⁴.

As the urbarium demonstrates, the town hall was not only the administrative center of the market, but also the commercial one. In 1672, on the ground floor of the town hall there were small shops rented by craftsmen, the meat and the bread vending area, "Fleischbanken" and "Brothaus" respectively. The "Grund- und Salbuch" specifically names five bakers, three butchers, two potters, a rope maker, a flour merchant and a grocer, everyone paying the rent, "Stüfftgeld", to be represented in the town hall with their business. Furthermore, the bread supervisor of the town, "Brothüter"⁵⁵ Ludwig Prompper, lived in the town hall.

The urbarium describes the rooms in the city gates in detail: in the gate on the Small Danube, "Kleine Donau", in the south of the municipality, known as the "Kleines Donautor" (Fig. 5, I), the civil servant "Bürgerdiener" Simon Seidl and the day-worker Martin Renner lived at close quarters. The shop of the local "Freimetzger", a butcher which slaughters ailing cattle, Georg Paucher and a house belonging to the town were also located at "Kleines Donautor". The bricklayer Balthasar Grabmair lived there. In the gate on Danube, "Große Donau", in the north of the municipality, known as the "Großes Donautor" (Fig. 5, II), was the locksmith's shop of the Weng locksmith family. In the gate into the "Au", riparian area in the west of the market, the "Autor" or "Auertor" (Fig. 5, III), the market town provided four rooms free of charge, the poor family ("erarmbte Burgersleith") Pauman living there.

Figure 4. Signer of the "Grund- und Salbuch". Simon Khueffer, grocer (inner council), Tobias Winhardt, baker (municipal administration), Michael Hekhmair, brewer (mayor), Eggidius Fiedler, brewer (outer council), Sebastian Scheffthaller, butcher (outer council), Wolfgang Hafner, dyer. In brackets the respective offices or areas of responsibility in the market town, taken from the council minutes of 1672 (VCA B-1-2).

⁵⁴ Pfügl, Joseph: Vohburg mit seinen Ortsteilen im 20. Jahrhundert. Vohburg 1998.

⁵⁵ Riepl, Reinhard. The bread supervisor administrated the transactions between bakers and customers in the "Brothaus", the guild house and vending are of the bakers. In addition to size, weight and quality, the price was often specified.

Figure 5 – Part 1. Reconstruction of the places mentioned in the “Grund- und Salbuch”.

Figure 5 – Part 2. Reconstruction of the places mentioned in the “Grund- und Salbuch”.

Figure 5. Rekonstruktion der im Salbuch erwähnten Orte. Drawn outlines are based on the earliest known detailed town map of Vohburg (1813)⁵⁶. **(a)** Vohburg and surroundings. Arabic numerals 1-4 mark the Vohburg community gardens “Gabesgärten”. **(b)** Reconstruction of the “Pälzen”, today’s “Baizen” area. **Main map:** The main buildings have been marked with Roman numerals. I: “Kleines Donautor”; II: “Großes Donautor”; III: “Auertor”; IV: “Bruckstadl”, the bridge barn; V: Shooting range at the “Pälzen” (exact location unknown); VI: Schoolhouse (exact location unknown); VII: St. Andreas; VIII: St. Anton; IX: rectory; S: “Spital”, hospital and almshouse. Buildings I-VI were owned by the town. The two-letter acronyms in the figure are assigned to the respective persons from the main text. The two letters indicate the profession. Bā: baker; Bd: civil servant; Bh: bread supervisor; Br: brewer; Fā: dyer; Fi: fisherman; Fm: “Freimetzger”; Gb: court messenger; Gl: glazier; Gs: court clerk; Gw: innkeeper/host; Hp: potter / stove setter; Kh: cowherd; Km: grocer; Ld: leathermaker; Lo: lodenmaker; Ma: bricklayer; Me: flour merchant; Ml: painter; Mz: butcher; Mü: Müller; Pf: piper; Sc: shoemaker; Se: ropemaker; Sm: blacksmith; Sn: tailor; Ss: locksmith; Sw: “Seelweib”, traditional female mortician; Ta: day-worker; Wa: wainwright; We: weaver; Wg: white tanner; Wm: knacker; Zm: carpenter; X: unknown occupation; Z: abroad; †: deceased. *: house inhabited by the indicated person. **: “Gmainhaus”, communal house inhabited by the indicated person. °: garden, meadow, field or another place associated with the given person. []: House destroyed during Swedish occupation.

After the schoolhouse (**Fig. 5**, VI) was destroyed in war times, it was subsequently rebuilt by the market town Vohburg. In 1672 it was located on the castle hill⁵⁷ and was rented by the painter Constantinus Dosch, paying an annual rent of 2 fl. The town also owned the “Hüthaus” (lit.: herding house) am “Spitalgraben” (trench at the hospital), next to the community gardens⁵⁸ (**Fig. 5**, No. 3), in which the local knacker Georg Litter lived (**Fig. 5**, Wm). Remarkably, the knacker's shop is located close to inhabited buildings, the communal houses “Gmainhäuser” at the “Gries” residential area. This is highly unusual, because the knacker’s profession was considered dishonorable and dirty⁵⁹, which is why the shops of knackers were located far from settlements. The urbarium also mentions that the knacker Georg Litter had extensively cleared away east of his workshop, i.e. downstream of the Small Danube. The urbarium calls this whole area “Gries”. Unlike the “Gries” residential area in the south of the town center, the “Gries” downstream was not yet settled, but served as a pasture, overgrown with fruit trees and wild scrub (**Fig. 5**, “Viehweiden-Gries”). This undeveloped area was constantly built over the following centuries - including a newer knacker's shop (Griesstraße 58) - and is still known to the people of Vohburg as “Gries”. The civil mill “Neumühle” was owned by the town as well. Its construction was commissioned by Duke Stephen III the Magnificent in 1398. The mill is located 1.5 km south of today's city center on a branch of the Ilm, just before it forms the Small Danube together with the Wellenbach. At that time, the miller Andre Heuss lived in the “Neumühle”, which also housed a sawmill. Around the mill there were gardens and fields, which the town considered to be associated with the mill, as well as a large and a small community garden (**Fig. 5**, No. 1&2) in proximity.

By far the largest space in the urbarium, however, is taken up by the description of the 34 inhabited community houses “Gmainhäuser”. These were dwellings owned by the municipality and rented out for 10 kr⁶⁰ per year. We can reconstruct three of Vohburg’s “Gmainhaus” settlements from the descriptions in the urbarium: the settlement at the “Gries”, then the one at the “Pälzen” and another one behind the castle “*hinter der Pürg*”. The reconstruction of these settlements turns out to be manageable in almost all cases, particularly because of the detailed descriptions of the neighborhoods.

For the “Gmainhaus” settlement at the “Gries”, on today’s Griesstraße, we know that it consisted of two rows of houses located on one street outside the town walls, alongside the Small Danube. The northern row of houses went from the home of the fisherman Martin Hörman, living in his communal house between the Small Danube bridge and the Small Danube Gate “[...] *clain Thonaupruckhen und des clain Thonauthors*“ (fol. 4v), up to the last inhabited house, the knacker’s shop. The nearby hospital also serves as a reference point. Starting at the bridge on the other side of the street, the southern row of houses reached from the white tanner’s workshop (Caspar Lehner’s) to Georg Seiz’s communal house and the shoemaker Andre Reitter in his “*Behausung am Griss*” (fol. 6r). The “Grund- und Salbuch” also shows that the white tanner's workshop in this “Gmainhaus” settlement probably belonged to the municipality which only rented it to the white tanner Lehner. The blacksmith in the settlement at

⁵⁶ Bayerische Landesbibliothek Online. Ortsblatt für Vohburg an der Donau von 1813, accessed on January 22, 2022.

⁵⁷ Kopp, Max. 2017.

⁵⁸ Subdivided herb gardens. Citizens could rent this community gardens from the city and grew vegetables in these.

⁵⁹ Nowosadtko, Jutta: Scharfrichter und Abdecker. Der Alltag zweier „unehrlicher Berufe“ in der Frühen Neuzeit. Paderborn 1994.

⁶⁰ Currency: 1 fl (Gulden) = 60 kr (Kreuzer) = 480 hl (Heller).

the “Gries”, Bärtholome Schneider, had to pay 30 kr annually because his forge was built on land owned by the market town.

In the “Gmainhaus settlement” at the “Pälzen” (today: Baizen; Bahnhofstraße 5-40), the former shooting range⁶¹ serves as a reference point (Fig. 5, V). The shooting range should have been located roughly where the house numbers 14/16 of Bahnhofstraße are today. It burned down around 1742 during the Austrian occupation. Starting from the shooting range, which the day-worker Simon Liebhardt rented from the city, one can reconstruct the settlement south of the Small Danube. It is also worth mentioning that there were further community gardens to the east of the “Pälzen” area, today's Regensburger Straße (Fig. 5, No. 4).

The communal houses behind the castle are presumed to be on today's Burgstraße and Hohenstaufenstraße, in the northwest of the castle mountain. These “Gmainhäuser” were located quite loosely around the “Auertor”, with a trench in the south (“Augraben”) and the “Oxengraben” in the north (see Fig. 5). The latter was a meadow used by the civil servant for meadows and acres (field guard = “Auhüter”) / carpenter Phillipp Rorekher. Being framed by the road, the “Auertor” gate, the Danube, and the houses outside the gate, the location of the “Oxengraben” can be made out very precisely by the descriptions in the urbarium.

Beyond that, there was a single communal house next to the bridge barn (“Pruckhstahl”; Fig. 5, IV), which the fisherman Veith Mathes (inner council) lived in and a communal house of the fisherman Michael Eyring, which was located at an unspecified trench. Additionally, two communal houses are mentioned that were uninhabitable because of the damages originating from the Thirty Years' War (fol. 7v) - along with their former residents, the deceased Hanns Eisenmair and Paull Strasser. The urbarium states that these destroyed buildings would have to be reclassified as communal houses after their renovation and, like the others, should therefore be assessed at 10 kr per year. However, the location of the destroyed houses cannot be defined: there are no clear geographical indications, only the neighbors are listed.

Apart from these exceptions, the “Gmainhaus” settlements can be reconstructed very well from today's perspective. The details of the people living there and their neighbors prove to be helpful in forming an overall impression of the place in 1672.

Analysis of the professions

In addition to this geographical interpretation, the “Grund- und Salbuch” allows a comprehensive analysis of the professions of the persons who are mentioned in the urbarium of Vohburg in 1672 (Fig. 6). For most people, the text indicates the occupations. Only a few text passages do not mention a profession. In order to assign those people without any information to their profession, the author refers to the council minutes of 1671-1673 (VCA B-1-2/1-3). The first pages of these council minutes list the people (together with their job) who have assumed responsibility in the municipality for the period of corresponding time (e.g., as members of the inner and outer councils). Since these protocols have not yet been transcribed and analyzed, only the people on the first few pages have been included.

All persons who can be clearly classified geographically were added to the reconstructed map with an acronym (Fig. 5). These markings represent their places of work, places of residence (*, **) or gardens, fields and meadows (°) mentioned in the urbarium.

The Salbuch lists eleven fishermen: Peter Engseugl (Fi1), Michael Eyring, Martin Hörmann (Fi3), Nicolaus Matthes (Fi4), Veith Mathes (Fi5), Wolf Mez (Fi6), Wolf Pless (Fi7), Hanns Schelshorn/Schelsthorn (Fi8), Reichardt Scheuder, Leonhardt Wüntter (Fi10), and Jacob Zollinger (Fi11).

Sixteen people are listed as day-workers. These were Mathes Daser (Ta1), Jacob Eyring (Ta2), Georg Grädl (Ta3), Thoma Hueber (Ta4), Hanns Khormiller (Ta5), Hanns Liebhardt (Ta6), Simon Liebhardt (Ta7), Thoma Pökh/Pölk (Ta8), Georg Seiz (Ta9), Leonhardt Rauchegger (Ta10), Marthin Renner (Ta11), Adam Rhormair (Ta12), Caspar Weltmair (Ta13), Michael Widtman (Ta14), Hanns Wolf (Ta15), and Michael Zieribl (Ta16). There are also three cowherds, Thoma Pölk, Leonhardt Rauchegger, both referred to as day-workers, as well as Jacob Schöberl (Kh).

The urbarium counts sixteen people who, according to today's understanding, produce, trade, and monitor food. This includes five bakers Georg Schreder (Bä1), Hanns Schwarzgrebmer (Bä2), Johann Winhardt (Bä3), and his

⁶¹ Probably a place for shooting practice.

son Tobias Winhardt (Bä4), as well as Mathias Winhardt (Bä5). Andreas Heuss (Neumühle, Mü1) and Bartholome Neuhauser (Hartacker, Mü2) are mentioned as millers. The local flour merchant (“Melber”) was Georg Wagner (Me). The bread supervisor Ludwig Prompper (Bh) took care of the bread supplies. In addition, three butchers, Hans Koch (Mz1), Adam Prunner (Mz2), and Sebastian Scheftaller (Mz3), as well as the “Freimetzger” Georg Paucher (Fm) are mentioned in the urbarium. Georg Doppler (Br1) and Michael Hekhmair (mayor, Br2) are mentioned as brewers. The former was “Burgsass”⁶² in Vohburg. Based on the council minutes, Eggidius Fiedler could be identified as a brewer. The brewer Jacob Haider has already passed away. His deceased widow Barbara (Br4) is mentioned in the Salbuch. The brewer Thomas Haider listed in the council minutes is possibly their son. It is also evident from those records that in 1672 another brewer, Bärtlme Leichtl, and another butcher, Veith Königer, were residents in Vohburg.

Among the twelve people who are involved as craftsmen in the processing or production of clothing, the “Grund- und Salbuch” counts four weavers, namely Zacharias Eyring (We1), Hanns Khienast (linen weaver), Melchior Pauman (linen weaver, We3) and Nicolaus Rieschl (We4). It names three tailors, Sebastian Khueffer (Sn1), Jacob Schmit (Sn2), and Michael Thalhammer, as well as the lodenmaker Sebastian Tanner (Lo). Sebalt Maister (Ld) is listed as a leathermaker, Andre Reitter (Sc) as a shoemaker and Wolf Hafner (Fa) as a dyer. Apart from the white tanner Caspar Lehner (Wg), no other tanner is mentioned in the urbarium. The mentioned council minutes demonstrate that in 1672 there was another white tanner in the municipality, Johann Riedl, and another shoemaker, Thomas Jenich.

Eight people are named as craftsmen who are to be classified in the construction industry in today's sense. These include the carpenters Georg Rorekher (Bruckmeister, Zm1) and Phillipp Rorekher (field guard, Zm2), as well as the two bricklayers Balthasar Grabmair (Ma1) and Andre Hofner (Ma2). Likewise, the two potters / stove setters Jacob Rapp (Hf1) and Thoma Trattner (Hf2), the painter Constantinus Dosch (Ml) and the glazier Wolf Hueber (Gl).

Furthermore, the urbarium describes seven craftsmen who processed iron and wood or produced craft materials. These were the locksmiths Wolf Weng (Ss1) and his son Andre Weng (Ss2), and the blacksmith Bartholome/Bärtlme Schneider (Sm). It names Hanns Wippinger as cooper, Hironimus Miller (Wa1) and Willibaldt Schneider (Wa2) as wainwrights. Likewise, the rope maker Michael Prändl (Se). The cooper Mathes Geser is also listed on the first pages of the above-mentioned council minutes.

Apart from the craftsmen, the grocer Simon Khueffer (Km), the civil servant Simon Seidl (Bd), the court messenger Ludwig Khiener (Gb) and the musician / piper Jacob Veichtmair (Pf) are mentioned. In addition, two morticians (Sw1, Sw2), „*das alt: und Junge Seellweib*“ (fol. 2v), are described, who took care of the sick, poor and dying. From the urbarium, it can be concluded that the “Kastenknecht” Simon Burger (Kk), a lower official, oversaw the holdings of the Bavarian authorities, such as the granary⁶³. The court clerk was Georg Vetter (Gs). The local knacker was Georg Litter (Wm). The unpublished transcriptions of VCA B3 show that Georg Rhaitt, mentioned in the urbarium, was an innkeeper/host (Gw). From the first pages of the council minutes, which have not yet been transcribed, it can also be reconstructed that there were two other innkeepers in Vohburg in 1672, namely Gabriel Hölzl and Simon Hueber, and another grocer, Hanns Sezensackh.

The people who are mentioned in the urbarium but for whom no profession is known are Hanns Furthmer (X1), Georg Hiemair (X2), Georg Paumann, and his wife (X3, X4), the citizen Bartholomäus Prunauer (X5), the citizens Gallus Schiechel (X6), Anna Schneider (X7), Anna Seiz (X8), and Reichart Steichel (X9). There is also no known occupation of the two deceased Hanns Eisenmair (†1) and Paul Strasser.

Besides the miller Bartholomäus Neumair from village Hartacker in the south of Vohburg, there are several “foreigners” mentioned in the urbarium, namely the farmers Hanns Widtman (Z1) from Menning in the northwest of Vohburg, Sebastian Hueber (Z2) from Pleiling in the north of Vohburg, Wolf Aman (Z3) from Dünzing in the east of Vohburg, and Hanns Knöferl (Z4) from Hartheim in the north of Vohburg. All of these villages have been incorporated into the modern city of Vohburg over the last century which would make the “foreigners” citizens of Vohburg in nowadays dimensions. Lastly, the brewery administrator Johann Spizwegg from Kelheim (in Lower Bavaria) is also mentioned in the urbarium, owning a piece of land at the “Tierwiese” (cannot be identified geographically).

⁶² Kopp, Max. 2017. page 40. The “Burgsass” inhabits and/or takes care of a castle, serving the lordship.

⁶³ Riepel, Reinhard. Kastenamt.

Figure 6. Analysis of the persons mentioned in the “Grund- und Salbuch” by profession. **(a)** Number of people within an occupational branch (in Vohburg, 1672). Light brown: mentioned in the urbarium. Dark grey: reconstructed by the council minutes (VCA B-1-2/1-3), see main text. The respective sectors were defined in today’s sense. Food: Professions that produce, trade, or oversee food. Clothing: Professions involved in the processing or production of clothing. Iron/Wood: Professions in which iron and wood are processed or crafting materials are produced. **(b)** Professions of the “Gmainhaus” (communal house) tenants mentioned in the Salbuch, and **(c)** their position in the market town.

Acres and meadows of the town

The “Grund- und Salbuch” provides details of the meadows and fields belonging to the market, neighboring the property of further people who were citizens at that time. The meadows that belonged to Vohburg were almost exclusively in the “*Auveldt*”/“*Aufeld*” – an area that, according to the maps from 1813, was between the settlement at the “*Pälzen*” and the village Hartacker – and in “*Underriedt*”/“*Unterried*”, which is likely to be located in the south of Hartacker (Fig. 5, a). The town had only three acres: one near the “*Pälzen*”, another in “*Mitterfeldt*” (without geographical assignment) and a third, which was called “*Thaimbakher*” (also without assignment). The forest stock of the municipality was even smaller. It only consisted of the “*Auholz*” at the Danube, in the west of Vohburg, next to the meadows of the village Irsching, and the “*Gstokhet*”, a scrub area in the alluvial forests.

The urbarium divided the meadows which were meant for haying into two categories: those that the town leased and those that were given free of charge to Vohburgers with special community services. Twelve of the leased meadows were located in “*Unterried*”, and the citizens could draw annual lots for their use. These so-called “*Loswiesen*” or “*Losäcker*” (lottery meadows) were quite common in Bavaria at the time⁶⁴. There were other lottery meadows near the “*Neumühle*” and near the village Hartacker. The “*Sechzger*” meadows, the “*Dreyschilling*” meadows and the “*Eglsee*” are mentioned in the urbarium and can be classified geographically in the “*Unterried*”. Furthermore, a meadow bordering Hartacker, which was called the “*Mos*”. In this, both Vohburg’s citizens and villagers from Hartacker were allowed to mow without paying a fee. Meadows in the “*Aufeld*” were given to the field guard Philipp Rorekher and the bridge guard Georg Rorekher for their services. The latter was also given a meadow on the Ilm. The municipality gave meadows to the three cowherds Thoma Pölkh, Jacob Schöberl, and Leonhardt Rauchegger, called “*bey der Welln*” (in west of Vohburg, towards the village Irsching), for their service. The cowherds were also allowed to mow at the “*Mos*” near Hartacker, as were their colleagues from Hartacker. And finally, the civil servant Simon Seidl was allowed to mow a meadow in “*Unterried*” and cultivate the three municipal fields described above without a lease.

⁶⁴ Riepl, Reinhard. Losacker.

Financial analysis

Besides the geographic and social insights that can be gained from the “Grund- und Salbuch” one thing must not be forgotten: at the time the document was mainly used for bookkeeping. It was primarily a list of all the city's properties and the annual rents that accrued as a result. This financial aspect is briefly outlined below. A detailed financial classification such as in the dissertation by Elisabeth Able⁶⁵ for a later point in time is expressly not intended at this point.

Figure 7. Income of Vohburg listed in the Salbuch for the year 1672. The color coding from Fig. 5 was adopted (dark red, red, light red: official buildings of the town; light brown: communal houses (“Gmainhäuser”); purple: community gardens; gray: meadows and others).

The income of Vohburg for the year 1672 (listed in the urbarium) amounts to a total of 80 fl 28 kr (**Fig. 7**). The town took in 21 fl and 20 kr a year from renting out the shops in the town hall. The premises in and around the city gates brought the municipality 13 fl, half of which (6 fl 30 kr) came from commercial use by the locksmith Weng and the butcher Georg Paucher. Renting out the apartments in the schoolhouse on the castle mountain, in the shooting range at the “Pälzen” and the knacker’s shop at “Spitalgraben” brought in 8 fl a year. Smaller items, such as a pigsty belonging to the court messenger Ludwig Khienner, are listed here as “miscellaneous in the town centre”, at a total of 1 fl 39 kr 4 hl a year. The communal houses already discussed in detail were rented annually at 10 kr per house, making a total of 5 fl 40 kr.

The community gardens accounted for a large proportion of the annual income listed in the urbarium, namely 18 fl. The gardens were divided in “Bifang”⁶⁶ units of which one was 4 kr to rent. The largest community garden was at “Neumühle” (130 “Bifang”; **Fig. 5**, No. 2), then the gift garden at “Gries”, almost as large, adjoining the city (128 “Bifang”; **Fig. 5**, No. 3; “*Plachgries*”, see inset “#” from 1748) and finally the much smaller gift garden near “Neumühle” (12 “Bifang”, **Fig. 5**, No. 1). The “*Pflanzgarten*” (fol. 9r) near the “Pälzen” was made available free of charge (**Fig. 5**, No. 4). And finally, the meadows for haying/the hay harvest, most of which were leased to the residents of Vohburg as lottery meadows: the rent for an area representing a day's work ranged between 36 kr for a double-harvest-meadow and 16 kr for a one-harvest-meadow. In total, the community's meadows brought in 12 fl 48 kr 4 hl.

⁶⁵ Able, Elisabeth. 2008.

⁶⁶ Riepl, Reinhard. Elevated part of a furrow. A “Bifang” was probably about 1 m wide and 100 m long.

Around half of the income listed in the urbarium can be attributed to the leasing of meadows and community gardens. The other half is renting out community-owned buildings. The amount that originates from the 34 communal houses every year is strikingly small. The annual rent for one of these communal houses, 10 kr, is remarkably low compared to wage levels at the time: a day-worker in the early Electorate of Bavaria (1648-1700) usually earned 15 kr per day⁶⁷. A hot meal with a drink in a tavern costed 10 kr, which is exactly the annual rent for a communal house in Vohburg.

The urbarium only lists the revenue from the municipal property. It does not give any details on wealth, trade, or citizen tax, which of course the residents had to pay in addition to the leases and rents given here. Unfortunately, a list of all taxable citizens from this time has not been preserved and can only be found in the VCA for the year 1745 (VCA B8). For example, the baker Hans Georg Wünhardt⁶⁸ paid a wealth tax of 5 fl 20 kr 5 hl (0.24%) and a citizen- and trade tax of 34 kr 2 hl in 1745. As a contrast to this, the fisherman Bärtlme Wüntter⁶⁹ (estimated value of his possessions: 65 fl), for example, paid a wealth tax of 9 kr 2 hl (0.24%), as well as a citizen- and trade tax of 7 hl⁷⁰. Without a suitable adjustment for inflation, these figures can hardly be put in relation to those in the urbarium – a reconstruction would be imprecise and vague. It is therefore difficult to classify the income mentioned in the urbarium financially and it is impossible to record the municipal budget under these circumstances.

⁶⁷ Drexler, Toni: Historische-Werte-Datei: Preise, Löhne, Erträge für den Raum westliches Oberbayern und Schwaben östlich des Lechs, 2007. <https://www.blf-online.de/historische-werte-datei-preise-loehne-ertraege>; accessed on February 6, 2022.

⁶⁸ VCA B8: Entry No. 1, fol. 14v.

⁶⁹ Bartlme Wüntter can also be found in the handwritten notes from 1748 on the last page of the urbarium (#).

⁷⁰ VCA B8: Entry No. 156, fol. 66v.

Discussion

Historical interpretation

The “Grund- und Salbuch” urbarium from 1672 offers a unique view at the structures of the market town Vohburg in the period following the Thirty Years' War. It provides insights into the geographic and social structures of the Bavarian municipality, which had around 500 inhabitants at the time. The urbarium clarifies names for geographic areas that are no longer common today and demonstrates how much the town owned and earned through leases.

The interpretation of the “Gmainhaus” / communal house settlements, which were at the “Gries”, at “Auertor” gate, and at the “Baizen” on the outskirts of what was then the town center, is particularly relevant to the history of the city. The evaluation showed that the tenants of the communal houses consisted mainly of day-workers and fishermen and were therefore significantly poorer than the townspeople who were represented with their shops in the center of the village (Fig. 6, b). In addition, the residents of the communal houses were greatly underrepresented in the administration of the market: of 34 tenants, only two fishermen, Martin Hörmann (outer council) and Veith Mathes (inner council), had access to Vohburg's decisive circles (Fig. 6, c). The fact that the knacker Litter, who was considered dishonorable, lived next to the “Gmainhaus” settlement at the “Gries” emphasizes the precarious situation of the “Gmainhaus” residents all the more. Additionally, the knacker's unusual location within the “Gmainhaus” settlement indicates that the municipality probably expanded by leaps and bounds beyond the old town limits (the town wall from the Small Danube Gate to the hospital) and created living space for poorer residents. The group of less-trained craftsmen and day-workers was needed by the wealthy Vohburg bourgeoisie in order to find their way back to normality and to grow again after the devastating war time. The division in a poor class and the richer, more powerful bourgeoisie could have caused a special, perhaps even tense situation. This is indicated by a strike by Vohburg craftsmen and day-workers for higher wages in 1653, during which the council fined the rebels⁷¹. Nevertheless, the almost symbolically low rent for a communal house suggests that the market was actively pursuing settlement policies to keep the poorer residents in Vohburg. The “rewards” in the form of complimentary meadows and fields, with which the municipality honored the services of the cowherds, the field- and bridge guards, and the civil servant, points in the same direction.

In contrast to the class of day-workers and fishermen, the “Grund- und Salbuch” illustrates the Vohburg bourgeoisie as a group of people who were (1) represented in the town hall both administratively and commercially, (2) owned their own property in front of the town, such as the brewers Hekhmair and Haider (fol. 11v, 12v), and (3) lived presumably separated from the day-workers within the old town limits. Based on the location of the communal houses, the above-mentioned old city limits can be reconstructed (Small Danube Gate - hospital - today's Alte-Landgerichtsstraße - “Großes Donautor” Danube gate - today's Hohenstaufenstraße – “Auerthor” - castle hill - parsonage). Vohburg's farmers with property were also part of the wealthier class, however, they are not explicitly mentioned in the urbarium. It can be assumed that some of the people for which the urbarium does not give any profession are farmers. A detailed analysis of the council minutes of 1671-1673 (VCA B-1-2/1-3) and the finalization of the publication on the “Lengenprunnerfeldt” of 1664 (VCA B3) could cover this blind spot in Vohburg's city history.

Significance for the genealogic research

Documents such as the “Grund- und Salbuch” are also valuable for genealogical research because they provide details on ancestors and living conditions at the time. A prime example of the analysis of such a document was published by the local historian Josef Auer in 2012 with the transcription of the “Mirakelbuchs des Seligen Bauern von Vohburg”, a book of miracles by Vohburg's “saint” (lit. “the Blessed Farmer”)⁷². The article sheds light on the pilgrimage to the “Blessed Farmer”, which was and still is mostly limited to Vohburg and the surrounding area, and gives a complete list of answered prayers and witnesses to miracles between 1694 and 1821. The pilgrims are named by name, profession, and place of residence. It includes names of the families Enseigl/Engseugl, Eyring, Haider, Höckhmair/Hekhmair, Scheftthaller, Schelchshorn/Schelshorn, etc. which are also mentioned in the VCA documents for this period.

⁷¹ Kopp, Max. 2017. Page 40.

⁷² Auer, Josef: Das Mirakelbuch des Seligen Bauern von Vohburg. BBLF, Volume 75, 2012. pp. 12-89.

Figure 8. Exemplary pedigree for the Vohburg citizens Ignaz Kruegsperger, white tanner, with Anna Winhardt, baker's daughter from Vohburg⁷³. Italics: ancestral numbering in the author's pedigree (Sosa-Stradonitz system⁷⁴). According to current knowledge, the Winhardt family came from Schrobenhausen⁷⁵. It is uncertain where Jakob Haider Sen. is from, the same applies to the white tanner Ignaz Kruegsperger. It is assumed that the latter came from a family of white tanners who were then based in Pfeffenhausen (Lower Bavaria).

The urbarium from 1672 contains a plethora of useful information which helps to find ancestors and sheds light on their living conditions. An example of this can be observed for the personal genealogical research of the author, whose ancestors Matthias Winhardt, Jakob and Barbara Haider are mentioned in the urbarium (**Fig. 8**). Like his father Jakob Haider Sen. (born around 1585), Jakob Haider Jun. (born around 1615, probably in Vohburg) was a brewer and a citizen of Vohburg. According to the church records of the parish of St. Peter in Vohburg, Jakob Haider Jun. was the father-in-law of the baker Matthias Winhardt, whose name can also be found in the urbarium. On July 11, 1673, Matthias Winhardt married Agathe Haider, the daughter of Jakob and Barbara Haider, forming a bond between two bourgeois families of Vohburg. Their daughter Anna Winhardt, born on July 20, 1681, married the white tanner Ignaz Kruegsperger on December 11, 1711, in Vohburg. The white tanner Kruegsperger was later chamberlain of Vohburg⁷⁶ and is mentioned for the year 1718 in the mentioned book of miracles as "*Bürger und Weissgärber*"⁷⁷. The descendants of Ignaz Kruegspergers are still at home in Vohburg and the surname Krugsperger is still local.

In summary, the present study demonstrates that the "Grund- und Salbuch" can bring genealogical research in Vohburg to life. To the mentioned names, it assigns a concrete place of residence and profession, and in the case of Jacob Haider even the name of his wife and their property. Therefore, it is an important source of information for the in-depth analysis of Vohburg's (citizen) families in the 17th century. As soon as the church records for Vohburg in the episcopal archives of the Diocese of Regensburg - at the present stage not yet digitized and available on the internet - are made accessible to a broad public, one can assume that many more exciting insights into the genealogy of Vohburg's citizens will be revealed.

⁷³ Church records parish of St. Peter, Vohburg, Diocese of Regensburg.

⁷⁴ Kekulé von Stradonitz, Stephan: Ahnentafel-Atlas. Ahnentafeln zu 32 Ahnen der Regenten Europas und ihrer Gemahlinnen. Berlin, J. A. Stargardt, 1898–1904.

⁷⁵ Genealogie Kiening. Winhard Christoph, born in 1580, Schrobenhausen; Winhard Johann, oo 1640 in Vohburg.

⁷⁶ VCA: Municipal finances 1745.

⁷⁷ Auer, Josef. 2012. Page 55, Entry No. 400.

Drawing on the church records, the “Grund- und Salbuch” (1672), the description of the “Lengenprunnerfeldt” (1664), as well as on the council minutes of 1671-1673, we will be able to paint a holistic picture of the town after the Thirty Years' War, a picture that would – without any doubt – help to better understand Vohburg and its rich history.

Abbreviation

VCA: Vohburg City Archive (“Stadtarchiv Vohburg an der Donau”).

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Corresponding author

Dr. Philipp Heckmeier, Zurich (Switzerland), philipp@heckmeier.net, ORCID: 0000-0002-7311-977X

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Vohburg City Archive (VCA)

B3 Description of „Lengenprunnerfeldt“, 1664.

B6 „Grund- und Salbuch“, 1672.

B8 Tax register market town Vohburg, 1745.

B-1-2 Council minutes, 1671 und 1672.

B-1-3 Council minutes, 1673.

R-1/83 Municipal finances, 1745.

Episcopal Archive Regensburg

Church records of the parish of St. Peter, Vohburg.